

AI-assisted Sound Design with Audio Metaphor (AuMe): An Evaluation with Novice Sound Designers

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Abstract

The rapid advancement of artificial intelligence has led to growing scholarly interest in the application of AI tools to support creative practices across various disciplines. This study investigates the integration of AI-assisted tools into sound design practice, with a focus on the Audio Metaphor (AuMe) soundscape generation system. Conducted with 71 novice participants, the research addresses a central challenge of novice learners: overcoming initial technical barriers while fostering foundational creative skills. Through a systematic comparative evaluation of traditional and AI-assisted instructional approaches, this study examines the effects of AI integration on learning experiences, creative outcomes, and the balance between technical skill development and creative exploration. The findings aim to inform future design and integration of AI tools into creative practices. Results indicate improved efficiency and performance, with users showing moderate to slightly positive acceptance of the AuMe system.

1 Introduction

1.1 Motivation

Rapid advancement of artificial intelligence has sparked significant interest in the use of AI tools to improve creative practices in various domains (Zhou and Lee, 2024). This research investigates the integration of AI-assisted tools in sound design practice, specifically focusing on the use of Audio Metaphor (AuMe) in an undergraduate sound design course with 71 novices.

The primary challenge in learning sound design lies in obtaining technical abilities while developing fundamental creative skills. For novices, the need to simultaneously master technical operations and engage in creative exploration can be particularly demanding. This steep learning curve can inhibit early experimentation and the development of a unique artistic voice. Building on the findings of several studies that demonstrate the potential of AI tools in supporting novices in technical fields

(Tchemeube et al., 2025; Kazemitabaar et al., 2024; Kosar et al., 2024; Zheng et al., 2024), this research changes focus to investigate the specific impact of tools such as AuMe. We explore how AuMe influences novice practice performance and creative outcomes in the context of sound design, examining its capacity to bridge the gap between technical accessibility and creative expression.

1.2 Audio Metaphor System

Audio Metaphor (AuMe)¹ is an AI-assisted sound design tool that has been continuously developed since 2012 (Thorogood et al., 2012). It employs natural language processing (NLP) techniques to parse user prompts, then retrieves appropriate sound samples from freesound.org based on specified duration, clips them, and intelligently arranges them on a timeline. Unlike contemporary AI technologies that directly generate audio, AuMe focuses on assisting users in the selection, editing, and composition of soundscape (Thorogood and Pasquier, 2013a). Through successive iterations, the system has incorporated affective computing through valence and arousal (Fan et al., 2016, 2017), enhanced background/foreground sound classification capabilities (Thorogood et al., 2015, 2017), and improved soundscape emotion recognition functionalities (Fan et al., 2018). These developments culminated in Audio Metaphor 2.0, which offers improved classification and segmentation pipelines (Kranabetter et al., 2022), establishing it as a significant innovative tool in the field of sound design (Thorogood, 2021).

AuMe is a generative sound design system that, unlike many post-2020 AI systems that directly generate audio through deep learning, such as MusicLM (Huang et al., 2023), aligns more closely with traditional sound design workflows as the classification framework described by Kamath et al. (2024). The system processes natural language inputs to retrieve and arrange audio files from a database, offering a “gentler” approach particularly suited for novice learning. Newbies still practice fundamental skills such as layering and editing while receiving AI support. For this experiment, AuMe has been configured to export directly to Reaper sessions, allowing seamless integration with traditional digital audio workstation workflows.

2 Research questions and objectives

2.1 Primary Research Question

How does the integration of AI-assisted tools (specifically AuMe) into novice sound design practice impact experience and creative outcomes? Through this question, we aim to understand the comprehensive effects of integrating AI tools in creative practice, particularly focusing on the balance between technological assistance and pedagogical value.

2.2 Supplementary Research Questions

RQ1: How does the integration of AI-assisted tools (specifically AuMe) impact novice sound designers’ workflow efficiency, user experience, and acceptance? This question examines quantitative time metrics, qualitative experience aspects, and factors influencing adoption, drawing from frameworks on human-AI interaction, usability, and acceptance in creative systems (Tchemeube et al., 2023; Kamath et al., 2024).

RQ2: How does AuMe influence novice performance and learning outcomes in sound design practice? Based on research on the impact of AI on artistic creation (Zhou and Lee, 2024) and AI in education (Kazemitabaar et al., 2024; Kosar et al., 2024), this question investigates both objective performance metrics and self-perceived improvement in sound design capabilities.

RQ3: What are the key challenges, including impacts on creative ownership, system trust, and learner autonomy in integrating AI tools (specifically AuMe) into sound design practice? This question examines technical and pedagogical challenges (incorporating the balance between human agency and AI assistance (Kazemitabaar et al., 2024)) and identifies potential opportunities for enhancing sound design learning through AI integration, drawing insights from co-design explorations (Zheng et al., 2024).

¹The Audio Metaphor system is web-accessible and can be found at: <https://audiometaphor.ca/>

Figure 1: AuMe System

2.3 Research Objectives

We evaluate AI in sound design across dimensions: workflow efficiency and user experience, learning outcomes and performance, and system capabilities and integration opportunities. Efficiency is compared between traditional and AI methods by timing five workflow stages (sourcing, AI-assisted sourcing, editing, composition, mixing) to determine stage-specific impacts. Performance is assessed through a combination of grader evaluations and novice self-ratings. grader evaluate the novices' technique, creativity, overall quality, and learning objectives (see Tables 1 and 2 for the full rubric), while novices provide a self-rating on a 1-10 scale. User experience is measured using the CSI (Cherry and Latulipe, 2014) (exploration, expressiveness, immersion, iteration), SUS (Brooke, 1996) (usability), and custom questionnaires (workflow, future use, ownership, satisfaction) tailored to our pedagogical context.

3 Related work

Within AI creative practices, Zhou and Lee (2024)'s study found text-to-image AI significantly boosts productivity but can affect content novelty over time, revealing a critical tradeoff between efficiency and originality. However, Louie et al. (2022) showed AI music tool efficiency in idea exploration isn't guaranteed, depending heavily on interface accessibility and design; poor interfaces hinder productivity, while well-designed ones allowing user shaping/adjustment improve both process and output quality. Specifically for sound design, Kamath et al. (2024)'s investigation of professional interactions with generative AI informs effective AI-human interaction design for creative support tools in this domain. These studies collectively suggest well-designed AI tools, appropriately

balancing automation with designer control and creative agency, hold significant potential to enhance sound design performance.

While substantial data indicate AI tools enhance efficiency (Noy and Zhang, 2023; Paradis et al., 2024; Cui et al., 2025) and other studies show the effectiveness of these tools in student practice/learning exercises (Kazemitabaar et al., 2024; Kosar et al., 2024), both research directions are predominantly programming-focused. Conversely, research specifically using AI for audio creation often shifts focus to interaction or user experience (Louie et al., 2022; Tchemeube et al., 2023), rather than collecting actual efficiency improvement data. Although Tchemeube et al. (2023) observed their AI music system provided "efficient and structured workflows" lowering barriers for novices, their study lacked comprehensive timing analyses across creative production phases. This leaves a significant research gap regarding comparative efficiency analyses of AI assistance during creative production phases, especially when novices use AI tools for learning and completing sound design tasks.

A comprehensive AI tool evaluation must also focus on human-AI interaction in creative contexts (Zheng et al., 2024). For instance, emphasized transparency and clear documentation for AI in project-based learning. Evaluations by Tchemeube et al. (2023, 2025) of the co-creative Multi-Track Music Machine are particularly relevant, revealing tensions between user control and AI assistance—users appreciated novelty and ease of use but struggled with controllability. This dynamic relationship is further underscored by studies from Louie et al. (2022) on steering interfaces and (Kamath et al., 2024) on sound designer interactions. Therefore, besides examining effectiveness and efficiency, this paper evaluates the user experience of participants interacting with AuMe, capturing their perspectives on using AI-assisted creative tools.

Table 1: Rubric of Assignment 1-a (without AI-Assisted)

Criteria	Pts
Requirements & Constraints:	
1. 50-70 seconds in length, 8 or more sounds, 4 sounds recorded by yourself.	
2. 4 track minimum, 1 automation minimum, 15 seconds or less of recognizable speech.	
Final project bounced to 44.1kHz, 16bit, stereo wave file.	
3. Description of your work, a cue sheet or list of the sounds used.	
4. All necessary files and folders are present	10 pts
Technical requirements: signal to noise ratio, no clicks & pops, volume control, no distortion	2 pts
Aesthetics & final result: Did the artwork achieve what you described?	
How well was it mixed? How good did it sound?	3 pts
Total Points:	15

Table 2: Rubric of Assignment 1-b (with AI-Assisted)

Criteria	Pts
Requirements & Constraints:	
1. 50-70 seconds in length, 8 or more sounds, for Project 1b with Reaper and AuMe, the composition must use between 8 and 800 recorded sounds, sound effects and found sounds, including 4+ recorded sounds by yourself and 4+ sounds using the AuMe system (Please indicate this in the cue sheet).	
2. 4 track minimum, 1 automation minimum, 15 seconds or less of recognizable speech.	
3. Final project bounced to 44.1kHz, 16bit, stereo wave file.	
4. Description of your work, a cue sheet or list of the sounds used.	
5. All necessary files and folders are present.	10 pts
Technical requirements: signal to noise ratio, no clicks & pops, volume control, no distortion	2 pts
Aesthetics & final result: Did the artwork achieve what you described?	
How well was it mixed? How good did it sound?	3 pts
Total Points:	15

4 Research design and methodology

4.1 Experimental Design

Our study took place over ten weeks in an introductory sound design course for third-year undergraduates (see figure 2). During the first four weeks, novices receive instruction in traditional sound design methods and complete Assignment 1-a. In this initial assignment, novices develop soundscape compositions based on self-selected themes. They must source their own audio materials through various means, including personal recordings and sample libraries, then compose their soundscapes using traditional digital audio workstation (DAW) techniques.

The fifth week marks a significant transition with the introduction of the AuMe system. During this week, we collect surveys regarding Assignment 1-a and provide comprehensive training on AI-assisted workflow methods. Novices then proceed to Assignment 1-b, where they revisit their original themes from Assignment 1-a but with the aid of Audio Metaphor. This paired assignment structure allows novices to explore the same creative concept through different methodological approaches. While working with AuMe, novices can leverage the system’s ability to suggest and source relevant audio materials based on natural language prompts, potentially streamlining the resource gathering and composition process.

To evaluate the submissions, course grader assessed both technical proficiency and creative achievement using standardized course grading rubrics (see Table 1 and Table 2). The initial research design called for a single-blind study, where the grader would not be aware whether the assignment they are evaluating was AI-assisted or not. However, pedagogical constraints in implementation meant that grader were aware of which assignment version they were reviewing.

Figure 2: AuMe Study Plan and Process

4.2 Technical Implementation

Our technical implementation is focused on a new version of the AuMe system, wherein tracks can be exported directly as Reaper session files. These session files contain complete track information and all necessary audio files, enabling seamless integration with traditional digital audio workstation workflows. Importantly, as the system has been shown not to be human-competitive (Thorogood and Pasquier, 2013a), it positions the ‘last mile’ of the creative process to be human-driven. This implementation allows novices to transition smoothly between AI-assisted generation and manual editing, facilitating a workflow that balances the system’s generative capabilities with the novice user’s creative agency and final decision-making.

4.3 Data Collection and Analysis Methods

Our data collection strategy integrates multiple measurement approaches to capture both quantitative and qualitative aspects of the novice experience. For efficiency assessment, we track completion times across various sound design tasks, examining the entire creative process from sound sourcing to editing, composition, and mixing. Participants maintain detailed work session records, providing granular data on time allocation and workflow patterns.

The evaluation of creativity support and output quality employs objective and subjective measures. The Creativity Support Index (Cherry and Latulipe, 2014) provides a standardized framework

for assessing how well AuMe facilitates creative expression. Given the individual nature of the assignments in this study, the 'Collaboration' dimension from the CSI instrument had been excluded from our analysis.

User experience data collection involves a comprehensive array of instruments. The System Usability Scale (Brooke, 1996) offers a validated measure of tool usability, while our custom comparative questions specifically address novices' experiences with both traditional and AI-assisted methods. These questions investigate the differences in satisfaction between the two approaches, helping us to more thoroughly evaluate the value of the AI tool. Open-ended responses allow participants to articulate their experiences in detail, providing rich qualitative data for thematic analysis.

4.4 Validation Mechanisms

To ensure data quality and reliability, we implement several validation mechanisms. Attention check questions are embedded within the surveys to verify participant engagement. The self-reported time logs undergo cross-validation through comparison with qualitative feedback.

4.5 Limitations

Our study has several limitations. The sequential design, with traditional methods preceding AI use, poses a methodological challenge: while pedagogically sound for scaffolding learning (ensuring foundational skills before AI), it introduces experience as a confounding variable experimentally. We plan a reversed-sequence study next year to mitigate this learning effect and allow for more robust cross-comparison. Generalizability may be limited by our single-institution (SFU) context and specific novice population, as factors like demographics can moderate AI acceptance and creativity (Ma et al., 2025). Further limitations include technical differences in audio output formats (AI-generated MP3 vs. traditional uncompressed formats) and reliance on self-reported time logs, which are subject to recall bias and varied diligence, potentially impacting the precision of efficiency analyses. Lastly, logistical constraints prevented a blind assessment, introducing potential evaluator bias; however, this risk was substantially mitigated by two key factors: the use of a detailed scoring rubric, and the grader is not affiliated with the development of AuMe.

5 Results and Analysis

5.1 Efficiency Analysis

Our analysis reveals a complex picture of efficiency gains and losses when comparing traditional (Assignment 1-a) and AI-assisted (Assignment 1-b) approaches. Initial data shows a 21.83% reduction in overall task completion time, decreasing from 606.48 to 474.10 minutes. However, this apparent improvement requires closer examination across different stages of the sound design process. Given the right-skewed distribution of our time data and presence of extreme values, following (Leys et al., 2013), we employed the Wilcoxon signed-rank test as our primary statistical method. The test results demonstrated significant differences across all workflow stages: overall time using ($p = 0.0002$, $r = 0.7916$), sourcing ($p < 0.0001$, $r = 0.9045$), editing ($p < 0.0001$, $r = 0.8751$), composing ($p < 0.0001$, $r = 0.8833$) and mixing ($p = 0.0123$, $r = 0.7586$). All stages showed statistical significance at the $p < 0.05$ level, indicating consistent and meaningful differences between traditional and AI-assisted approaches.

Beyond the substantial reduction of 45.5% in sourcing time, the significant decreases observed in subsequent stages - Editing (-40.5%), Composing (-43.1%) and Mixing (-31.1%) are particularly notable. This pattern suggests that AuMe's contribution may extend beyond mere asset retrieval, potentially aiding novices in making creative decisions more efficiently during the core constructive phases of editing and composition. While mixing involves technical adjustments, the time reduction here might also point towards AI assistance facilitating quicker aesthetic choices or resulting in material that requires less corrective mixing effort.

Participants were asked to adopt an AI-assisted priority strategy, first generating initial audio materials via the AuMe system (provided as a DAW project) and subsequently using traditional sound design techniques for modification. Importantly, even after accounting for the AI interaction time (covering prompt engineering, generation processing, and project download), the overall duration for this task

Table 3: Time Comparison Between Traditional (Assignment 1-Part1) and AI-Assisted (Assignment 1-Part2) Methods (Minutes, Mean)

Phase	Assignment 1-Part1	Assignment 1-Part2	Change (%)
Sourcing	133.2295	72.6066	-45.50%
Editing	182.6613	108.7258	-40.48%
Composing	149.3871	85.0000	-43.10%
Mixing	141.2097	97.2258	-31.15%
Using AI	Nil	110.5410	
Overall	606.48	474.0992	-21.83%

phase still showed a decrease. Qualitative feedback indicated that the increase in interaction time with AI was sometimes driven by user interest in exploration rather than task complexity. As one novice noted, "I spent more time than necessary experimenting with different prompts because I was curious about what the system could generate," a view shared by other participants, suggesting that the observed AI interaction time often included exploration beyond core task requirements. Consequently, it is possible to suggest that as users become more familiar with a specific AI tool, this exploratory time overhead may diminish, potentially leading to further reductions in interaction time during future repeated use.

5.2 Performance Assessment

Performance analysis revealed statistically significant improvements in both expert and self-rated assessments when using the AI tool compared to traditional methods. Expert assessment, conducted by the course grader, showed a substantial mean improvement of 14.12%; a paired t-test confirmed this difference was highly significant ($p < 0.0001$). Self-rated scores also demonstrated a significant positive shift, with an average increase of 11.17% (paired t-test, $p = 0.0177$). Given the nature of the assessment scores (effectively using a 1-point interval), the results from these parametric t-tests are expected to closely correspond with those from a non-parametric equivalent, such as the Wilcoxon signed-rank test. Qualitatively, this improvement was reflected in novice preferences: 33 novices rated their AI-assisted work higher, 19 preferred their traditional work, and 11 rated them equally. Furthermore, in open-ended responses, 42 out of 56 novices explicitly stated that the system helped enhance their sound design performance. As one novice commented, "The system helped me find better quality sounds and gave me inspiration for the composition." However, this technical enhancement was accompanied by mixed feelings regarding creative agency, articulated by another novice who reflected, "While I could achieve better technical results, I sometimes felt disconnected from the creative process when relying on AI suggestions." These responses underscore the complex interplay between improvements in technical proficiency and the subjective experience of creative satisfaction in AI-assisted sound design Zhou and Lee (2024); Louie et al. (2022).

Figure 3: Self-Rated Performance: (Left) Box Plot, (Right) Distribution.

5.3 User Experience and Acceptance

The overall user experience was evaluated through standardized metrics and qualitative feedback. The Creativity Support Index (CSI) (Cherry and Latulipe, 2014) assessment yielded a median score of 68.0 (mean = 66.9, SD = 13.3), indicating good creative support. The System Usability Scale (SUS)

Figure 4: Lecturer-Rated Performance: (Left) Box Plot, (Right) Distribution.

(Brooke, 1996) showed similar results with a median of 65.0 (mean = 64.3, SD = 13.9), suggesting acceptable usability but with room for improvement.

Detailed analysis of user feedback revealed a nuanced picture of system acceptance. Among the 71 participants, 25 provided predominantly positive feedback, focusing on the system's ease of use and efficiency. For example, one novice emphasized the intuitive interface: "The system was straightforward to use and quickly provided usable sounds." However, 13 novices offered mixed responses that balanced benefits against limitations, and 15 provided neutral feedback, suggesting uncertainty about the system's capabilities.

Workflow preferences showed a clear trend, with 46 novices (65%) preferring the AI-assisted workflow compared to 25 (35%) favoring traditional methods. However, when asked about future use intentions, the response was more measured: 41% indicated definite interest in future use, 38% expressed uncertainty, and 21% were disinclined to use the system again. The specific contexts for potential future use were notably varied, with 11 novices specifically mentioning inspiration-seeking, 7 for sound sourcing, and smaller numbers indicating potential use in music production (5), time-constrained projects (5), and ambient sound design (4). This aligns with observations about AI tools being used for specific stages like ideation or sourcing (Kamath et al., 2024).

The system's user-friendliness received a moderate rating of 5.10 out of 7, with control aspects scoring slightly higher at 6.66 out of 10. However, qualitative feedback highlighted several pain points: "Unexpected Outcomes" was mentioned by 21 novices, "Prompt Input" challenges by 9 novices, and "Lack of Controllability" by 6 novices. This difficulty reflects a known challenge in human-AI interaction, often termed the 'interpretation gap,' particularly evident in text-to-audio systems where nuances in prompts can lead to significantly different outputs (Huang et al., 2024) (Tchemeube et al., 2023). As one novice noted, "The valence-arousal parameters were confusing and seemed to have little effect on the output." highlighting user confusion with these controls. These valence-arousal parameters, based on Russell's circumplex model (Kranabetter et al., 2022), build on established soundscape emotion frameworks (Fan et al., 2018; Thorogood and Pasquier, 2013b). While theoretically sound, our findings suggest novice users need more transparent mapping between these controls and their perceptual outcomes, along with improved documentation and interface design.

In response to the open question asking if AuMe helped improve their sound design and in what ways, 42 out of 56 participants providing detailed feedback answered affirmatively, while 14 responded negatively. The data reveals a significant majority found the system helpful, primarily citing reduced sound sourcing time (25 mentions) and achieving better creative outcomes (16 mentions). However, among the 14 participants who found it unhelpful, a notable theme emerged: 9 mentioned using the system solely for sourcing, suggesting it did not enhance their core design process. It should be noted that individual responses could be assigned multiple codes, hence the mention counts do not necessarily sum to the total number of affirmative or negative responses.

5.4 Creative Ownership and System Trust

Our investigation into creative ownership perceptions revealed a distinct divide among novices. Among all participants, only 9 reported a strong sense of ownership over their AI-assisted work, while 20 felt moderate ownership, another 20 reported limited ownership, and 22 indicated no sense of ownership at all. This distribution suggests a significant challenge in establishing creative ownership

Table 4: Thematic Code of Question: Did you find the usage of the system helped you do sound design better? And In which ways.

Positive Answer	Count	Negative Answer	Count
Yes	42	No	14
Reduce Sourcing Time	25	Only useful for Sourcing	9
Creative Outcome	16	Hard to find Short Clips	3
Reduce Editing Time	4		

when using AI tools, a recurring theme in human-AI co-creation (Zhou and Lee, 2024; Tchemeube et al., 2023, 2025).

The relationship between ownership perception and system trust showed interesting patterns. While 28 novices reported moderate trust in the system, and 13 indicated high trust, their confidence was primarily limited to basic functionalities. As illustrated by the qualitative feedback, 13 novices found ownership through the prompt creation process: "I think adding the right keywords and specifics helped lead AuMe towards the direction I was seeking." Conversely, 14 novices viewed prompt input as insufficient for creative ownership: "I'm only typing an input to the system, so I don't think I own authorship."

A notable pathway to ownership emerged through post-processing activities. Eight novices specifically identified editing and mixing as key to establishing ownership, with comments like "After the audio was generated I usually made a lot of edits and mixing so it would fit in my composition." This suggests that interaction designs allowing for manual refinement and integration might be crucial for fostering a sense of creative ownership in AI-assisted workflows (Louie et al., 2022; Kamath et al., 2024). The most significant challenges to building trust were interpretation issues (19 mentions) and inconsistent outputs (12 mentions), consistent with user feedback in similar systems (Tchemeube et al., 2023). novices frequently expressed frustration with the system's interpretation of prompts: "If my description was too detailed, the system couldn't generate; if it was too vague, the output would not be what I wanted." This interpretation gap between user intent and AI output has been identified by Vear et al. (2023) as a critical challenge in human-AI musicking frameworks, where they emphasize the need for developing more sophisticated 'language' mechanisms for AI systems to better understand and respond to human creative intentions.

5.5 System Limitations and Challenges

Analysis of user feedback revealed several significant challenges in the AI-assisted sound design process. The most prominent issue was unexpected outcomes from prompt inputs, reported by 21 (29.6% of participants). This challenge manifested in two distinct aspects: prompt construction difficulties and system interpretation issues, a common theme in human-AI creative interaction (Tchemeube et al., 2023; Kamath et al., 2024). Unlike contemporary LLM-based systems, the AuMe platform employs earlier computational approaches to language processing (Thorogood and Pasquier, 2013a), which may contribute to interpretation challenges for users accustomed to modern LLM prompt patterns, particularly when crafting complex requests.

The valence-arousal parameter system emerged as a particular pain point, with 4 novices specifically noting that these parameters "seemed to have no effect" on the generated output. Additionally, novices reported challenges with sound quality (5 mentions) and repetitive outputs (4 mentions), suggesting limitations in the system's generative capabilities or database diversity.

Technical workflow issues also surfaced, particularly regarding post-processing requirements and file management. Ten novices noted difficulties in reviewing and organizing generated content, with comments like "going through each sound to figure out if it's worth using was time-consuming." This feedback suggests that while the AI system successfully generates content, the integration of this content into existing workflows requires further optimization, a key consideration for designing effective creative support tools (Kamath et al., 2024).

Table 5: Thematic Code of Question: What were the pain points of AuMe?

Pain Point	Count	Pain Point	Count
Unexpected Outcome (Bad interpretation)	21	Sound Quality	5
Prompt input challenges	9	Valence and Arousal not working	4
Lack of Controllability	6	Repetitive Outcome	4

6 Discussion

This research contributes concrete empirical evidence and practical insights into AI integration within creative practice. Our findings provide quantifiable data on efficiency gains, detailed analysis of creative output variations, and documented patterns of novice-AI interaction in sound design practice. These results will help establish evidence-based frameworks for implementing AI tools in creative practice while preserving pedagogical value, contributing to discussions on AI in education (Kazemitabaar et al., 2024; Kosar et al., 2024; Zheng et al., 2024).

The practical implications of our findings will primarily benefit novice learners and tool developers. Tool developers gain insights into the specific needs of novice learners. These insights can enable more targeted and effective feature development in future iterations of creative AI systems, building on existing interaction research (Louie 2022 expressive, Tchemeube 2023 evaluating, Kamath 2024). Furthermore, future work could employ co-design methodologies to better understand the needs of different user groups, such as comparing practicing musicians (Wainwright 2025 exploring) to the novice population studied here. For novice learners, this research not only sheds light on the benefits and challenges of using AI-assisted tools in their practice but also offers valuable insights to inform their decision-making on integrating such tools into their learning process.

The efficiency findings directly address RQ1, demonstrating that AI integration significantly impacts workflow efficiency across all sound design stages, with particularly notable time reductions in the creative phases of editing and composition. The findings of user experience and acceptance on user experience and system acceptance address key components of RQ1, revealing moderately positive usability metrics and workflow preferences, while identifying concrete challenges such as unexpected outcomes, prompt input difficulties, and limited controllability that directly influence user acceptance. Additionally, these identified interface and interpretation challenges contribute to our understanding of RQ3, as they represent significant barriers to learner autonomy and effective human-AI collaboration in sound design practice. The exploration of ownership perceptions and trust factors directly responds to RQ3, identifying significant challenges in establishing creative agency with AI tools, while also revealing potential pathways to enhanced autonomy through prompt creation and post-processing activities.

A deeper dive into the performance data via quartile distribution uncovered a distinct pattern related to novices' initial skill levels. The most significant gains were observed in the third quartile (the bottom 25% of performers), where novices showed a 24.14% average increase. This contrasts with a 12% increase at the median level and, notably, only a 7.48% increase for novices in the top quartile (those above the 75th percentile, or Q3). This distribution suggests that the AI tool may be particularly advantageous for novices less experienced in sound design, potentially by offering structured guidance or effective starting points. This aligns with findings in programming learning where AI assistants support novices (Kazemitabaar et al., 2024; Kosar et al., 2024), a finding echoed in ongoing research exploring various facets of AI integration in programming courses, including defining desirable characteristics for AI assistants (Denny et al., 2024), specific tutor integrations (Latoza et al., 2024), the use of tools like ChatGPT (Conrad and Wilkinson, 2024), and their complex effects on novice confidence and frustration (D'Souza et al., 2024). Conversely, novices who already had established sound design practices and resource preferences appeared to benefit less markedly. One high-achieving novice illustrated this, noting their reliance on consistent external resources ("I did use mostly YouTube sound effects in both assignments"). This pattern of diminishing returns for more experienced users mirrors findings by Cui et al. (2025), who observed that senior developers with established workflows gained less productivity improvement from AI coding assistants than their junior counterparts. It is crucial, however, to consider a potential ceiling effect in our assessment methodology. The maximum achievable score was 15 points, and while few novices neared this in the first assignment, a considerable number achieved scores above 14 in the second

(AI-assisted) assignment. This scoring limitation might have artificially compressed the observable performance gains within the top quartile. These performance results provide substantive evidence for RQ2, showing that AuMe positively influences both objective and self-perceived novice performance, with the most significant benefits observed among less experienced designers, though the relationship between technical improvement and creative satisfaction remains complex.

Furthermore, for educators who might consider applying similar AI-assisted systems in teaching in the future, this research provides an important forward-looking perspective. By examining the specific impacts of AI assistance on novices in sound design learning and practice, including its benefits and potential challenges, our study reveals the likely effects of integrating such tools on the learning process and student agency. While (Cheng, 2025) explored AI in music education, our study provides complementary insights in the domain of sound design, offering concrete empirical evidence on how AI tools affect novice learning experiences. These insights can help educators make more informed decisions when determining whether and how to incorporate emerging AI technologies into creative teaching, aiming to leverage technological advantages while maximally supporting student development.

7 Conclusion

This study investigated integrating the AI sound design tool AuMe with 71 novice undergraduates. We found AuMe significantly boosted workflow efficiency and improved project quality (assessed by grader and self-ratings), particularly benefiting initially lower-performing students, likely by providing better sounds and inspiration (Cui et al., 2025; Kazemitabaar et al., 2024; Kosar et al., 2024). User experience (CSI/SUS) was generally favorable, and most preferred the AI workflow. However, significant challenges emerged: future use acceptance was cautious due to usability issues (prompting, control) and unpredictable outputs, echoing known human-AI creative interaction problems (Tchemeube et al., 2023; Huang et al., 2024). Concerns about creative ownership and autonomy were prevalent (Zhou and Lee, 2024; Tchemeube et al., 2023), though post-processing offered a path to reclaim ownership, suggesting AI's potential as a partial workflow partner (Louie et al., 2022; Kamath et al., 2024).

These findings imply educators need careful pedagogy for AI tool integration, addressing usability, teaching interaction strategies, and discussing ownership. Developers must create more predictable, controllable, and transparent AI that supports user agency and integrates better into workflows (Louie et al., 2022). Despite limitations (sequential design, self-reported time), future work should explore longitudinal effects, alternative AI/interaction designs, and fostering collaboration. In conclusion, while tools like AuMe offer significant efficiency and novice support benefits, careful design and pedagogy are vital to ensure they augment creative skills, agency, and learning.

System Availability

General information about the Audio Metaphor (AuMe) project can be found at: <https://www.audiometaphor.ca/>. The specific version of AuMe used in this study, featuring the Reaper session export capability described herein, is publicly accessible online at: https://digitalmedia.ok.ubc.ca/projects/aume_v2/index_p.html.

Ethical Statement

Our ethical framework, approved under Simon Fraser University's minimal risk approval (Study Number: 30002733), prioritizes participant well-being and academic integrity throughout the research process. The informed consent process begins with a comprehensive web-based form detailing study objectives, procedures, participant rights, and the fact that this study has received delegated minimal risk approval. This information is then reinforced through a verbal introduction during class sessions, ensuring novices fully understand their role in the research. All consent documentation is securely stored and accessible only to authorized research team members.

Participation benefits extend beyond the immediate research context. novices gain valuable experience with both traditional and innovative AI-assisted sound design methods, enhancing their technical

skills and creative capabilities. The SONA bonus credit system² offers three credits for participation, with alternative credit-earning opportunities available for novices who choose not to participate. This approach ensures that research participation remains voluntary and does not disadvantage any novices.

Furthermore, AuMe utilizes a curated subset of audio data sourced from the Freesound.org repository. This specific dataset is maintained by the Music Technology Group (MTG) at Universitat Pompeu Fabra (UPF) in Barcelona.

The audio samples from Freesound.org included in this subset and employed within our research are governed by Creative Commons licenses. Based on Freesound.org's contribution guidelines, sounds are typically licensed under CC0 (Public Domain Dedication), CC BY (Attribution), or CC BY-NC (Attribution-NonCommercial). For the purposes of academic critique and review within this study, sounds under all these licenses are appropriate for use, as academic research constitutes non-commercial use, ensuring compliance with intellectual property rights and ethical standards for academic use.

Data protection measures include secure storage of all research materials, strict confidentiality protocols, and clear procedures for data removal upon request. Participants may withdraw from the study until week nine, before data analysis begins. After withdrawal, their data is completely removed from the research dataset and confirmed through written notification.

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²SONA is Simon Fraser University's research participation management system, accessible at: <https://sfu-siat.sona-systems.com/>

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